

**SIGNIFICANCE AND FUNCTION OF FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT FOR
DETERMINING BUSINESS RESULTS OF TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY
COMPANIES**

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***Abstract.** The term "leadership" comes from the Latin origin of the word "tanus" translated as "hand". The term "management" comes from an English word that is rooted in the French-English word "menage" which means "management" or "management". Management is a discipline that deals with researching problems, managing affairs, as well as controlling personnel. The importance of management lies in the need to ensure the efficiency of the company's functioning. Without management, resources would be wasted. The basic task of management in tourism and hotel industry is to plan the desired future of the hotel company and to realize that plan to the maximum extent. The financial analysis of the company's operations is of crucial importance when making a series of business decisions, and it is based on financial reports. The financial reports provide a functionally and time-rounded set of business processes in the company. The key external users are investors and creditors, actually stakeholders who provide capital.*

When it comes to reporting for the needs of external users, International Accounting Standards must be applied, while in reports for the needs of internal users, that is, managers who make business decisions, different analyzes can be performed in accordance with internal needs. Therefore, financial management deals

with the management of business finances and consists of five functions (financial planning, financial organization, selection of financial personnel, financial management, as well as financial control) Personal finance refers to financial planning and control of personal financial flows of cash inflows and outflows. As for business finances, they refer to the concept of financial management in the company. At the end of creating and presenting financial reports, financial management creates management decisions within the company based on the report. Accounting and formation forms the basis of management for making final business decisions. The management and accountants of the company's organization are primarily responsible for the accuracy and reliability of the data, i.e. information presented on the basis of prepared financial and other reports.

Management therefore has an obligation to report to stakeholders on the success of the organization's operations. Managers take over tasks from the owners of the organization with the aim of achieving the appropriate effect. The audit of financial statements includes checking (balance sheet, income statement, cash flows, changes in capital and notes. The audit is performed by a certified accountant who checks the accuracy of financial statements. Making human resource plans is actually anticipating the need for personnel and matching the individual with the organization. Quality personnel may be rejected and poor quality personnel may be received. According to the reception of new employees, the management must pay attention to the orientation, ie the transformation of the newly hired into an efficient individual, which can be determined by measuring the performance and analyzing his abilities, as well as the behavior of the employees during work activities. Labor force retention is achieved by providing satisfactory personal income, benefits, benefits, and the like.

Keywords: *financial management, personnel management, management functions, financial indicators, financial managers, accountant auditor*

1. INTRODUCTION

The term "leadership" is of Latin origin "tanus" translated as "hand". In the twentieth century, a new term came into use, the English word "management". The word "management" itself comes from the English word "management", which is rooted in the French-English word "ménage", which in its original meaning has the meaning of being a capable staff, doing something, managing something, and is best translated as "management" or "management". Management is a special scientific discipline, of a multidisciplinary character, which deals with researching the problems of managing jobs, enterprises and social systems. The concept of management is also defined as a process by which purposeful organizations are created, directed, maintained and operated through coordinated, cooperative human effort. From the aspect of management in tourism and hoteliers, a definition that is sufficiently comprehensive and adapted to the requirements of the modern environment. Management means the process of working with the help and cooperation of other people, in order to effectively achieve organizational goals, with the efficient use of limited resources in the conditions of a changing environment.

The importance of management lies in the need to ensure the efficiency of the company's functioning. Without management, resources and energy would be wasted. From year to year, the need for management grows, and therefore there is a tendency to increase the number of people involved in management tasks. Business conditions in the modern tourist market present exceptional challenges for managers, and at the same time have led to a situation where the importance of this activity has never been greater. Successful managers change the world, influence the creation of new products and services, and support the personal development of the people who work for them. The essence of management in tourism and hotel industry is actually human relations, i.e. efficient management of processes and people. The basic importance of management derives from these relationships because it represents a process of conscious and constant improvement, where we understand the intention or goal as its basic element. the fact that in the US every year around 100,000 companies fail.

Fig. 1. Presentation of the growth rate of profit in the company

Source: https://puntomariner.com/images/financial-performance-of-the-company_4.jpg

In Great Britain, that figure is slightly lower, but still large, around 30,000. The main reason for their failure lies in ineffective management. The basic task, even the need, of management in tourism and hospitality is to plan the desired future of the hotel company and to realize that plan to the maximum extent possible. The basic task, even the need, of management in tourism and hospitality is to plan the desired future of the hotel company and to realize that plan to the maximum extent possible. In order to translate various ideas into actions, managers must be ready to support, encourage and motivate workers who need to implement planned plans and decisions. In the late 1950s, due to rapid economic growth and rapid technological changes, financial institutions such as pension funds and insurance organizations experienced a great rise.

Therefore, the manager's responsibility towards:

1. *salaries to employees,*
2. *to creditors and shareholders,*
3. *state taxes,*
4. *billing providers.*

Managers are interested in the success of the company because it provides them with higher salaries, and also because they are often shareholders. There was a need to use scientific methods in making financial decisions and a modern approach to financial management was developed. In contrast to the traditional approach, the modern approach to financial management is based on rapid economic growth and technological changes, which caused the importance of the manager's responsibility for the success of the company to grow tremendously.

In addition to the problem of capital acquisition, he also deals with the assets and liabilities of the balance sheet. The main goal of financial management at the state level is to strengthen the system of social relations- so that the layers of society are not in an illegal state. Therefore, when making financial decisions, you should: *evaluate their consequences, try to reduce the costs of their implementation, etc.* The main financial goal of the company is profit maximization. For shareholders, the main goal is to maximize their assets. This is achieved by increasing the market value of shares.

2. THE SIGNIFICANCE AND ROLE OF FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT FOR THE BUSINESS OF TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY COMPANIES

Management is the science and art of managing people. Financial management is the study of all matters related to monetary problems, money creation, flows, investments, consumption, a multitude of complex actions in the economy, and profit flows in general. Financial managers must not only learn how to make money, but also how to save it. You can earn more income through finance than in any other field of production or service. They show how to work less and earn more. Financial management is an excellent opportunity in the modern business world. In today's world, far more is spent on finance than on trade transactions. The fact that ignorance of finances can ruin any company must also be taken into account, so care must be taken to ensure that the finances of an entity are entrusted to a correct financial

manager. Financial management is the management of financial affairs of a business entity (companies, organizations, institutions) [1].

In the theory of finance, different terms are used for economic entities such as:

1. *financial management,*
2. *business finance,*
3. *microfinance,*
4. *corporate finance,*
5. *financial management.*

Fig. 2. Financial management

Source: <https://cdn.wallstreetmojo.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Fianancial-Management.jpg>

The most common term used by today's financial managers in tourism and hotel companies is "financial management". [2] Business finance in the hotel and tourism industry primarily studies tasks such as: [3]

- 1) *financial functions,*
- 2) *liquidity and solvency,*
- 3) *sources/forms of financing,*
- 4) *management of business finances,*

- 5) *business policy,*
- 6) *planning,*
- 7) *organization,*
- 8) *management or records,*
- 9) *control, analysis and information,*
- 10) *cash flow planning,*
- 11) *working capital analysis,*
- 12) *securities or instruments of value,*
- 13) *financial assessments of investment and financial decisions,*
- 14) *analysis of working capital and the like.*

The main goal of business finance management is to stimulate the financial capital of the business entity at the maximum rate of return on investment, which is also the central motive of financial management. Creating a policy of optimal financial placements while dynamically maintaining the optimal degree of liquidity of economic entities is the goal of managing business finances. [4] The next important goal for companies dealing with hotels and tourism is profit maximization, i.e. gain. Therefore, this goal is directly related to the profitability of the investment, because the demand for profit maximization implies equally the demand for maximizing the yield for capital investors, that is, the demand for more effective and efficient use of assets.

Along with this goal is the goal of maximizing the profitability of the business, which is achieved through maximizing the value of the investment investment. Maximizing share prices of business entities is one, but not the most important, goal that is used very often in practice.

Fig. 3. Functions of financial management

Source: <https://d1m75rqqgidzqn.cloudfront.net/wp-data/2021/11/08152056/financial-management-functions-1024x576.jpg>

Fig. 4. Essential Elements of Forensic Accounting in Business

Source: https://www.slideteam.net/media/catalog/product/cache/1280x720/e/s/essential_elements_of_forensic_accounting_in_business_slide01.jpg

There are three practical reasons for this, which are:

- 1. investors follow the values of share prices and make investment decisions based on that,*
- 2. share prices are visibly present on the stock exchange and are publicly traded.*
- 3. share price is the basic measure of profit for shareholders, because they can be sold and cashed.*

Financial management has a special place in the management system, because finance is closely related to management, technology, resources, personnel, etc. Mistakes in financial management can lead to negative consequences in these areas; on the other hand, the sources of financial problems are often found precisely in these areas. In our country, as well as in other countries in transition, financial management is just gaining real importance, while in countries with a market economy, it has long since become an important scientific discipline and practical activity. Deficiencies in the planning process make it necessary for managers to react spontaneously to changes in business, without adequate preparation to deal with those changes in a conscious way. By planning, the company's activities are conceived in such a way that they lead in the direction of achieving its goals. Planning decisions, therefore, must be made in advance, and they refer to the jobs that need to be done, then to when those jobs should be done, as well as to who should do the given jobs. Managers also use plans as business standards, which are necessary for them to control the company's operations, by comparing what happened with what should have happened. [5]

3. MANAGEMENT OF FINANCIAL PERSONNEL IN TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY

People with their professional qualifications and role in the business process represent the personnel base of companies and other organizational systems. That is

why human resource management, in theory and in practice, is also called personnel management.

Fig. 5. Human Resource Management

Source:<https://community.nasscom.in/sites/default/files/media/images/HRM.jpeg>

This term includes human resource management activities and managers who perform these activities. At the same time, human resources management activities represent the personnel policy, which is carried out by top managers, as well as managers of business units and functions, with the help of the personnel department headed by the appropriate manager. The basic role of personnel management is to harmonize the number and structure of human resources with the planned scope and structure of the company's operations. It represents the backbone of achieving the strategic goals of the company as a whole and its business units.

On the other hand, operational management is responsible for the following activities:

1. *determining the need for workers,*
2. *their training and development,*
3. *evaluation of the work,*
4. *rewards,*

5. protection at work,

6. replacement of workers who left the company.

Human resources management or personnel management takes place on two basic hierarchical levels. In this sense, as is the case with management in general, it differs:

1. strategic management of human resources, i

2. operational management of human resources.

Strategic management of human resources is based on the general strategy of the company and on the strategy of its business units and functions. In this process, the human resources function of the company, whose bearer is the human resources department, plays an important role. The activities of the personnel function are manifested in the assessment of personnel needs and opportunities of the company, as well as tendencies in the development of education, and in the study of people's behavior in the work process.

Based on the knowledge gained in this way, the personnel department helps the company's management in choosing strategic solutions for human resources management.

The role of the personnel department in this sense is manifested in helping management in the process of conceiving and implementing the strategy: [6]

1. inventions,

2. 2 choice,

3. deployment,

4. rewards and

5. personnel promotion.

This role of the personnel department is based on a thorough analysis of the tasks performed in the process of the company's functioning. Such analysis includes:

1. job description,

2. grouping of jobs,

3. evaluation of jobs.

Fig. 6. Strategic Human Resource Management

Source: <https://www.hrmexam.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/1-1.jpg>

On the basis of job descriptions, information is obtained about workers and their responsibilities, as well as the role of those jobs in the functioning of the company. In this way, knowledge is obtained about the type and level of qualification of workers required for given jobs. The grouping or specification of jobs aims to provide information about the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities of workers to perform certain jobs. In this way, it is possible to carry out the specialization of workers, which contributes to the increase of labor productivity. The evaluation of jobs serves as a basis for evaluating and ranking jobs, so that awards and salaries of workers can be determined more objectively.

Fig. 7. Operations Human Resource Management

Source: <https://hr.university/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Difference-between-HR-Operations-and-People-Operations-1024x660.jpg>

Operational management of human resources includes the development of strategic personnel plans. In this sense, operational managers:

1. *determine the personnel needs plan and require the personnel department to find suitable employees,*
2. *carry out on-the-job training,*
3. *decide on salaries and other rewards of workers,*
4. *evaluate and rank workers in order to measure the mutual relationship in height*
5. *salary,*
6. *are responsible for the implementation of occupational safety and health protection measures for workers,*
7. *are responsible for the implementation of contracts with trade unions,*
8. *undertake measures to fill vacant positions,*
9. *perform the final selection of new employees.*

Considering the specificity of the role of man as a thinking and creative element of the production process, the management of human resources is conditioned by the relationships that prevail in the social environment. In this sense, operational management, in conducting personnel affairs, must take into account the legal regulations in the field of labor relations, then the trade union organization of workers, as well as other workers' rights. That is why it is necessary for operational managers to familiarize themselves in detail with their legal obligations, as well as with other obligations towards society, before making decisions and taking actions in the process of hiring, assigning and rewarding workers in their organizational segment of the company [6].

Therefore, people are the most reliable resource at the disposal of an institution, human resources are the factors on which everything in every organization depends. The efficiency of functioning, as well as the economy of every organization, depends on the treatment and management of human resources. Despite the fact that the management emphasizes the importance of people in success, it is evident that there are still great reserves, especially in the practical relationship to the organization in which people live and work. Human resource planning is about predicting the need for people and matching the individual with the organization. Workforce selection is a critical stage in providing the organization with quality people.

In it, high-quality ones can be rejected and low-quality ones can be received. Upon admission, the management must focus special attention on turning the newly hired into an efficient individual, which is determined by measuring the performance and analyzing his abilities, as well as his behavior. Labor force retention is achieved by providing satisfactory personal income, benefits, benefits, etc. All the listed elements directly affect the productivity of work in the organization, thereby improving the overall economy of organizational systems. [7]

Fig. 8. Employee Selection

Source: <https://s3-us-west-2.amazonaws.com/courses-images/wpcontent/uploads/sites/.jpg>

4. ANALYSIS AND PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF TOURISM AND HOTEL INDUSTRY

Financial reports are defined as "a set of information about the financial position, performance, changes in capital and cash flows of a company" and represent a functional and time-rounded set of business processes that took place in a company and as such form the basis of any rational analysis. All company activities are aimed at creating value for owners and creditors.

Creating value for these interest groups takes place through three activities:

1. *financial activities,*
2. *business activities,*
3. *investment activities.*

Financial activities determine the company's relationship with current and potential owners and creditors. These activities include obtaining capital from own and borrowed sources. The acquired capital from these sources is invested in the acquisition of fixed and current assets that enable the company to perform its activities. These activities are calculated on the investment of money previously obtained in financial activity. That is why the activities of investing money are called investment activities. The activity of a company materializes through the performance of business activities. Business activities are related to the realization of key revenues, namely sales revenue and other revenues, as well as key expenses (costs of depreciation, materials, wages and other costs). The company's business activities are reflected in the income statement. All the mentioned activities represent business events (transactions) that accounting records and summarizes in financial reports at the end of the business year.

Fig. 9. Types of Business Activities

Source: <https://cdn.wallstreetmojo.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Business-Activities.jpg>

All activities of a company are materialized in the following financial reports:

1. *balance sheet,*
2. *income statement,*
3. *cash flow statement*

4. report on changes in capital.

5. Notes on changes in capital

Investment activities are materialized in the balance sheet, as well as financial activities. The statement of cash flows and the statement of changes in equity are derived reports that are prepared on the basis of the balance sheet and the income statement. The term “*balance sheet*” refers to a financial statement that reports a company's assets, liabilities, and shareholder equity at a specific point in time. Balance sheets provide the basis for computing rates of return for investors and evaluating a company's capital structure, and:

1. A balance sheet is a financial statement that reports a company's assets, liabilities, and shareholder equity.

2. The balance sheet is one of the three core financial statements that are used to evaluate a business.

3. It provides a snapshot of a company's finances (what it owns and owes) as of the date of publication.

4. The balance sheet adheres to an equation that equates assets with the sum of liabilities and shareholder equity.

5. Fundamental analysts use balance sheets to calculate financial ratios. [9]

An “*income statement*” is one of the three important financial statements used for reporting a company’s financial performance over a specific accounting period. The other two key statements are the balance sheet and the cash flow statement. The income statement focuses on the revenue, expenses, gains, and losses of a company during a particular period. Also known as the profit and loss (P&L) statement or the statement of revenue and expense, an income statement provides valuable insights into a company’s operations, the efficiency of its management, underperforming sectors, and its performance relative to industry peers. And: [10]

1. An income statement is one of the three major financial statements, along with the balance sheet and the cash flow statement, that report a company's financial performance over a specific accounting period.

2. The income statement focuses on the revenue, expenses, gains, and losses of a company during a particular period.

3. An income statement provides valuable insights into a company's operations, the efficiency of its management, underperforming sectors, and its performance relative to industry peers.

The "cash flow statement" (CFS), is a financial statement that summarizes the movement of cash and cash equivalents (CCE) that come in and go out of a company. The CFS measures how well a company manages its cash position, meaning how well the company generates cash to pay its debt obligations and fund its operating expenses. As one of the three main financial statements, the CFS complements the balance sheet and the income statement. In this article, we'll show you how the CFS is structured and how you can use it when analyzing a company. And: [11]

1. A cash flow statement summarizes the amount of cash and cash equivalents entering and leaving a company.

2. The CFS highlights a company's cash management, including how well it generates cash.

3. This financial statement complements the balance sheet and the income statement.

4. The main components of the CFS are cash from three areas: Operating activities, investing activities, and financing activities.

5. The two methods of calculating cash flow are the direct method and the indirect method.

The "statement of changes in equity" is a reconciliation of the beginning and ending balances in a company's equity during a reporting period. It is not considered

an essential part of the monthly financial statements, and so is the most likely of all the financial statements not to be issued. However, it is a common part of the annual financial statements. The statement starts with the beginning equity balance, and then adds or subtracts such items as profits and dividend payments to arrive at the ending ending balance.

Fig. 10. Enterprise Financial Management

Source:https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/thumb/2/20/IFAC_Definition_of_MA.jpg

The general calculation structure of the statement is as follows: [12]

$$\textit{Beginning equity} + \textit{Net income} - \textit{Dividends} +/\textit{- Other changes} = \textit{Ending equity}$$

5. CONCLUSION

The company regularly analyzes its financial results (difference between income and expenses). The elements and causes of the obtained result are very diverse, so they should be analyzed separately. There may be a discrepancy between the desired and the actual financial situation. A critical discrepancy between the

desired and real state represents a financial problem. Any information of a financial nature can be used for financial analysis: bookkeeping, information from institutions of the banking system, information from stock exchanges, etc. The objectives of information analysis can be control and diagnosis of the condition, in forecasting the development of the company in which case, the diagnosis of the situation should be carried out first. Financial control is a set of measures and activities for checking the financial activity of the company, with the application of special forms and methods. Financial control confirms that financial policy, marketing and management achieve the set goals, or reveals financial problems (inconsistency...).

Control can be internal or external. External control is performed by various inspection and other state bodies, banks, etc. Internal control is carried out by their own control and supervisory services. The purpose and content of financial control is determined by the company's financial function. Financial control checks practically all operations that are carried out with the use of money: compliance with the law regarding the use of financial resources, financial condition, correct payment of taxes, etc. Information that enables financial management is found in bookkeeping and other records. Particularly important are the records on: the state of foreign currency accounts, the state of securities and insurance policies, approved but unused loans, debts and claims against creditors and debtors, etc. Financial information should include all information that is useful for financial decision-making. Information about: needs and sources of financial resources, inflow and outflow of funds, cash flows, financial placements. The development of finance has strengthened the role of financial management. Finance is changing from a descriptive study to a rigorous analysis and normative theory, from the area of raising funds to an area that includes asset management, capital allocation and valuation of companies in the overall market, from external analysis of companies to an area that emphasizes decision-making about the company. Financial policy aims at financial strength, and it is reflected in the principles. The principles of financial policy are interconnected, and the task of financial policy is their optimal equalization. They can be defined as

requirements that management must adhere to in order to maintain its status on the market, that is, if it wants to strengthen the financial strength of the company.

Results will be worse than planned if management does not adhere to these principles. In the twentieth century, with the penetration of Western schools of management, the English term management was generally accepted to denote the concept of management. In countries with developed market economies, the importance and necessity of a detailed study of the theoretical and practical scope from the domain of management and the role and importance of management in the company's operations is especially highlighted. Management has been defined by different authors and practitioners in numerous ways, depending on which aspect of the problem they wanted to emphasize. In general, the content of the definition of management has changed with the changing nature of the environment in which organizations operate. According to the Bible, the movement of the Israelites towards the promised land was slow, because it was spontaneous and insufficiently organized. Around 1500 BC, Moses solved the problem by creating groups and appointing their leaders and managers, thus facilitating and speeding up the arrival in the promised land. Many authors use this example as the earliest attempt to generate useful ideas about the use of management for practical purposes.

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